

TOMATO DRYING AND STORAGE TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract

This article provides information on the technology of storage, processing and drying of tomato fruits. Based on the given information, scientifically based technologies are widely used in the processing and storage of tomato fruits.

Keywords: tomatoes, fruits, storage, processing, drying, industry, technologies, fertilizers, leaves, roots, productivity.

Introduction. All over the world, tomatoes are an important crop and an integral part of the human diet. While tomatoes are usually eaten fresh, more than 80% of tomato consumption comes from processed products such as tomato juice, ketchup, and sauce. Recent studies have shown the potential health benefits of a diet rich in tomatoes. Lycopene, a major carotenoid without provitamin activity present in red tomatoes, is responsible for their beneficial effects.

Nowadays, the demand for tomatoes is constantly increasing with the increase in population and preference for tomatoes. When tomatoes are processed into food, 10-30% of their weight becomes waste or "marm". Tomato pomace contains about 5% moisture, 12% fat, 27% protein, and 26% crude fiber. It is also

a fiber-rich food nabi and acts as a cholesterol-lowering feed in poultry products. Lycopene is produced from cold-dried tomato pomace using supercritical CO₂ extraction.

Tomatoes are rich in ascorbic acid, iron, and carotene. Along with being nutritious, it is a low-calorie boon. It has almost no connective tissue. Therefore, tomatoes are useful in digestive diseases. Due to its potassium content, it also strengthens the heart. Tomato and its juice are especially healing for pregnant and breastfeeding women.

Drying is a simple process of removing excess water from an agricultural or industrial product. This is the oldest method of food preservation. Most agricultural products contain 30-80% moisture, but around 75% is common for agricultural products. This moisture value is much higher than what is needed for long-term storage. Due to this moisture in the products, bacteria and fungi multiply very quickly.

Storing tomatoes is more difficult than other vegetables. However, it can be stored for 2-3 months. 60-70 g of tomatoes and 35-50 g of small-yielding varieties of tomatoes are stored well. The fruits of varieties with a high water content are not stored for a long time. The thickness of the tomato skin, the hardness of the core, and the resistance to melting determine its shelf life.

For storage, fully formed light blue tomatoes are picked with a fruit band. They should be undamaged, disease and pest-free, and not too small. Tomatoes are picked at various stages of ripeness, from fully red, underripe (pink and beginning to turn red), and pale blue to blue. Tomatoes are stored in crates in warehouses. In this case, the boxes are placed in two rows in width, eight to ten rows on top, and lengthwise as desired. It is recommended to leave a corridor of 0.6-1.5 m between the beds and 5-10 cm between the boxes. Red tomatoes can be stored for up to 30 days, plump ones for 40-50 days, and blue ones for up to 80 days. For the ripening of light blue tomatoes, the temperature should be +10 +12

0C. At a higher temperature, the ripening of tomatoes accelerates, and at a lower temperature, they quickly get sick. Ripe tomatoes can be stored in the refrigerator at -1 0C. The relative humidity of the air should be around 90-95%. Working with ethylene gas for 10 hours accelerates its ripening by 3-4 times. Tomatoes should be regularly monitored during storage.

Industrial drying of tomatoes. The nutritional value, pleasant taste, decorative red color, and coloring properties of tomatoes make them irreplaceable in the preparation of various food products. Tomatoes are canned separately and together with other components.

The dried product is produced in the form of tomato flakes or tomato powder. Crushed sun-dried tomatoes are added to sun-dried soups, soup mixes, and salad mixes. In addition to dried tomatoes, whole red pepper is added to such products.

It is advisable to use oval-shaped tomatoes for drying, because the "walls" of tomato fruits of this variety are very fleshy, and the amount of soft pectin substances that surround the seeds is not too high, which in turn makes it possible to obtain a high amount of finished product.

Due to the hard structure and small size of such tomato fruits, even slightly ripe fruits have a "good" resistance to mechanical shearing forces.

The dried product should be dark red or red, so fully ripe tomatoes are used for drying.

Tomatoes in a box brought for processing can be stored for a long time at low temperatures.

Tomato fruits processed in a continuous flow are dried in the following sequence. Tomatoes brought in for drying are loaded onto an inspection conveyor and unripe, blemished, or softened tomatoes are removed. The inspected fruits are washed in a washing machine with a fan.

Washed tomatoes are once again loaded on the inspection table, and the green bases, black spot areas, and leaf sheaths are cut off from the fruits.

In this case, the production capacity of one worker is 50...80 kg/hour, depending on the quality and size of the tomato fruit. After processing, the tomatoes are washed with a spray of water and directed to the cutting machine.

Circular disc machines equipped with transmission pipes with a diameter of 6, 7, and 10 cm are used for mowing. The size of the cut tomato slices is 6 mm.

From the shearing machine, the tomato pieces fall into a centrifuge, where they are freed from the pectin substances that surround the seeds, as well as the juice and, in turn, the seeds.

The "product" separated from the tomato slices is sent from the centrifuge's collector to the crusher using a pump.

The tomato slices are rinsed again in a spray stream in a fully mechanized line to prevent excessive adhesion to the drying surface.

Washed tomato slices are immediately sent to the drying chamber. Due to the high probability of the dried raw material sticking to the drying surface, it is advisable to dry tomato slices in special surface dryers or dryers equipped with Perlon filters. It is best to load the tomato slices to be dried on a cleaned drying surface, for which the drying surface is often treated with high-pressure steam. This treatment also ensures the microbiological safety of the finished product. The amount of loading of tomato pieces for drying depends on the type of dryer and is often up to 1...15 kg per 1 m² area.

Chamber, tunnel, and belt dryers are used for drying tomatoes. If there are opportunities, it is better to dry tomatoes with chamber and tunnel dryers until the moisture content reaches 18-22%, and then to continue drying in a belt dryer. If only chamber or tunnel drying is available for drying tomatoes, then the drying process is organized into three stages, and three devices of the same type are used for this purpose.

In chamber dryers, tomato slices do not mix when loaded from the upper chamber onto the trays, unlike other raw materials being dried, due to their smooth surface. Up to 70...75 kg of raw materials are loaded into one tray. The duration of loading time on the tray is 25...30 minutes. The temperature in the initial drying section is 64°C, and the temperature in the final drying section is 54°C. Final drying is carried out at 50°C in tumble dryers. Semi-finished products are dried to 10...14% moisture and the final product is dried to 8% moisture.

Slices of dried and cooled tomatoes are crushed and sorted. Grinding uses a 6 mm slotted blade, and 2.5 and 1.5 mm diameter blades are used for chopping. The content of crushed dried tomatoes can be 72-74% of large pieces, 16-20% of average, and 6-12% of small pieces. Peeled dried tomato slices are cleaned from color mismatches and metal impurities and packed in containers.

Conclusions

1. Judging from the conducted research, it was considered appropriate to pick fully formed light blue tomatoes with a fruit band for saving tomato fruits.
2. Ripe tomatoes can be stored in the refrigerator at -1 0C. The relative humidity of the air should be around 90-95%. Working with ethylene gas for 10 hours accelerates its ripening by 3-4 times.
3. When calculating economic efficiency, the rate of profitability was 147.1%.

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